

**Methylation risk score in peripheral blood predictive of conversion
from mild cognitive impairment to Alzheimer's Disease**

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Supplemental Tables

Table S1. Quality control process for primary DNA methylation data (GSE144858)

Subjects		CpG Sites	
Initial dataset	300	Initial dataset	410,942
Exclude four subjects with unknown conversion date	296	Remove sites with a detection p-value > 0 (82,090 sites removed)	328,852
		Retain only sites with cg annotation	328,094
		Exclude sites with a cis or trans mQTL	288,916
		Exclude sites with probe mapping issues or with a SNP (MAF > 1%) within 5 bases	251,491
		Retain sites with variance in the top quartile	62,873
Analysis data (96 controls, 107 MCI, 93 AD)	296	Sites included in analysis	62,873

Table S2. Demographics of European study subjects in primary and secondary datasets

	GSE144858	GSE153712
Age in years (mean +/- sd)	75 +/- 6.5	N/A
Sex (Female / Male)	177 / 119	400 / 326
<u>Disease status</u>		
Control	96	471
Mild cognitive impairment	107 (68 stable, 39 converted*)	94
Alzheimer's disease	93	161
* within one year		

Supplemental Figures

Figure S1. Histogram of beta values for CpG site cg09892121

Figure S2. Histogram of beta values for CpG site cg17292662

Figure S3. Histogram of beta values for CpG site cg25342005

Figure S4. Box plots of the MRS for all subjects across baseline disease states

Figure S5. Beta values for the CpG site cg09892121 across disease severity (all subjects, males only and females only)

Figure S6. Beta values for the CpG site cg17292662 across disease severity (all subjects, males only and females only)

Figure S7. Beta values for the CpG site cg25342005 across disease severity (all subjects, males only and females only)

Figure S8 Box plots of the MRS for all subjects in the secondary dataset across disease states

Figure S9. Box plots of the risk score with age and sex predictors

Figure S10. ROC curve for age and sex based risk score model with training data